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ABSTRACT

This research explored the complex cultural dynamics of matriarchy within Northern Thailand, focusing on Lanna traditions, amidst the prevailing patriarchy in broader societal and religious contexts. Employing a comprehensive method involving field visits, literature reviews, and engagements in Lawa, Lua, Karen, and Lahu villages, the study explored three primary questions: the perceptions shaping women's roles, their contributions to Northern Thai society, and the influence of implicit matriarchy stemming from ancient beliefs. Despite conventional expectations, the findings reveal women's significant impacts on the economy, spiritual practices, maternal duties, conflict management skills, and their distinct connections to land ownership. Historical narratives depicted women assuming roles in political and military leadership, underscoring the interplay between ancient matriarchal systems and dominant patriarchal norms. The study synthesized the coexistence of these influences, providing insights into roles of women in Northern Thai society. Furthermore, it offered recommendations for educators and community leaders to empower and promote the advancement of women in the region, thus fostering a more inclusive, gender-equitable, and culturally sensitive educational framework that contributes to broader societal progress and a peaceful community.

Keywords: Inclusive community education, Karen and Lahu tribes, Lanna Tradition, Lawa and Lua tribes, Matriarchy, Peacebuilding

INTRODUCTION

The historical context of Thailand, particularly during the era of its ruling kingdoms, reflects a strong patriarchal influence that shaped various facets of society. This patriarchal framework was evident in governmental leadership, family structures, and other societal institutions. The role of the monarchy, primarily led by male rulers, epitomized this hierarchical and gender-based structure. The King was seen not just as a political leader but also as a semi-divine figure, a tradition that reinforced male dominance and leadership.

Contrasting with this patriarchal dominance is the cultural environment of Northern Thailand, particularly the traditions inherited from the Lanna Kingdom. The Lanna Kingdom, which existed from the 13th to the 18th centuries, is now part of modern-day Northern Thailand (Williams, 2020). In certain Northern Thai communities, especially among ethnic groups such as the Karen, Lahu, Lawa, and Lua communities, matriarchal traditions are prominent (Comaposada, 2022). Property rights in these matriarchal societies are often transferred through the female line. Women have significant control over land and property, which is a stark contrast to the male-dominated inheritance practices in traditional Thai society (Tantiwiranond & Pandey, 1987).

In many Northern Thai communities, women manage family finances and agricultural activities, playing a crucial role in the local economy. Their economic empowerment reinforces their influential position within these societies. Lineage and inheritance follow matrilineal lines, passing family names, property, and social status through the mother (Tantiwiranond & Pandey, 1987). Cultural and religious practices also reflect matriarchal traditions, with women leading rituals and ceremonies, and female deities worshipped.

This research aimed to fill a significant gap in the literature on the roles of women, gender dynamics, and cultural practices within Northern Thai societies. By exploring the distinctive cultural context of the Lanna societies, the study sought to reveal the complex roles women play in both familial and communal spheres. The study focused on women's roles within Lanna societies, highlighting their influence in areas such as leadership, decision-making, property rights, and lineage.

The research has significant implications for education in Northern Thailand, highlighting the roles of women in these societies. Educators can use these insights to create inclusive practices that empower young women and girls, fostering their participation and leadership. By integrating Lanna's cultural strengths and gender dynamics into the curriculum, students gain role models and celebrate female empowerment, helping to dismantle gender biases. These insights guide the development of educational materials that reflect Northern Thai culture, showcasing female leadership from Lanna traditions. Understanding the cultural dynamics also aids in designing culturally sensitive educational programs, involving local women leaders to connect with students' cultural context.

This research was guided by three important questions. (1) What perceptions shaped the roles of women within family and community structures? (2) How did women contribute to the socio-cultural and religious framework of Northern Thai society? (3) In what ways did matriarchy shape the cultural and religious landscape of Northern Thailand?

The study focused on Northern Thailand, particularly Lanna traditions and matriarchal customs among groups like the Karen, Lahu, Lawa, and Lua. It examined women's roles in family, community, and religion but acknowledged limitations in representing the region's full cultural diversity. Future research could include more ethnic groups and adopt longitudinal approaches to

capture changes in societal norms over time. Language barriers posed challenges, suggesting the need for collaboration with local researchers fluent in regional languages. The study also noted the interconnected roles of men and recognized that factors like economic structures, education, religion, globalization, and modernization influence women's roles. For example, economic changes impact women's agricultural roles, and educational advancements can shift gender role perceptions and increase women's public participation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review explores various themes related to gender dynamics and indigenous societies. It explores into the matriarchal structure of the Ancient Lanna Kingdom, the evolving concepts of matriarchy and indigenous feminism, and the limitations and challenges within these frameworks. By integrating insights from both matriarchal theory and indigenous feminism, the review aims to foster a more comprehensive and inclusive understanding of gender roles.

Matriarchy in the Ancient Lanna Kingdom

The Ancient Lanna Kingdom, established in 1296, represents a notable period in Northern Thailand when the Lan Na Kingdom, or Lanna, emerged as a significant Tai kingdom (Encyclopedia Britannica, 2009). This period was notable for its matrilineal societal structure despite being a monarchy. Women played crucial roles in governance, family dynamics, and cultural traditions, contrasting the male dominance in many contemporary societies (Williams, 2020). Women in the Lanna Kingdom were involved in decision-making processes, both in public and private spheres (Panitchaphan, 2005). In this matrilineal system, lineage and inheritance were traced through women, giving them significant influence and power. Women participated in political, economic, and religious activities, shaping the kingdom's governance and culture. This

system promoted gender balance and made women's voices essential to the community's well-being and progress.

The Karen and Lahu ethnic groups, demonstrated strong matriarchal traits, with women holding central roles in community life (Comaposada, 2022). The Karen tribe, also known by various names such as Kayin, Kariang, or Kawthoolese, emphasized maternal lineage and ritualistic practices that emphasized the importance of women in maintaining cultural and social continuity (Neiman, 2008). The Lahu tribe embraced an egalitarian social structure, with equal roles and responsibilities for both genders. This matrilineal society promoted mutual respect and cooperation, challenging the traditional dichotomy of matriarchy versus patriarchy and showcasing the diverse social structures in the region (Waddington, 2022; 2023).

The Lawa and Lua, indigenous to the northern region, settled in valleys, unlike the highland-dwelling Karen and Lahu ethnic groups. Lawa societies were matrilineal, with mothers holding more authority than their sons, highlighting a nuanced matriarchal structure (Satyawadhna, 1991). However, the influence of dominant cultures led to their integration into the patriarchal framework, merging them into contemporary "Lanna" society as part of the Tai Yuan group. (Satyawadhna, 1991). In contemporary society, those called Khon Muang ('people of the cultivated land'), are the Tai Yuan group into which the Lawa and Lua have integrated" (Penth & Forbes, 2004).

These societies highlight the importance of women's role in governance to cultural preservation showcasing the complexity and richness of indigenous communities. By studying these practices, we not only deepen our understanding of historical gender dynamics but also recognize the diverse ways societies have valued and integrated women's roles, contributing to societal development and resilience.

Matriarchal Theory and Indigenous Feminism

Redefining Matriarchy

Matriarchy and Indigenous feminism have been the subject of historical analysis, revealing the governance structures of indigenous civilizations. According to Kears (2006), these societies were often led by matriarchs, elder women who held authority in familial and communal matters. Matriarchal systems in Indigenous cultures emphasized women's roles in decision-making, clan leadership, and family structures, challenging the Eurocentric view that women were inferior (Kears, 2006). These societies featured matrilineal governance systems, where authority and inheritance passed through the female line, contrasting with the patrilineal systems of many Western societies (Kears, 2006).

However, Sanday (2008) proposes a redefinition of matriarchy, emphasizing a balanced social system where both men and women play vital roles rooted in maternal social principles. This redefinition shifts the focus from the coercive power of authority to the persuasive force of tradition and cultural practices. In matriarchal societies like the Minangkabau of West Sumatra, tradition is upheld through the influence of both genders particularly senior women responsible for nurturing and maintaining social order (Sanday, 2003). Therefore, matriarchy characterizes a diffusion of power, where leadership and influence emanate from the preservation of social ties and traditions, continuity, and harmony through a balanced partnership between genders.

Limitations of Matriarchal Theory

While matriarchal theory offers valuable insights into the Indigenous governance it has limitations. It may reinforce gender binaries and exclude individuals who do not conform to traditional gender roles. By focusing on women's empowerment within a binary framework, this

theory may marginalize individuals who identify outside the traditional male-female dichotomy, such as non-binary and genderqueer.

The matriarchal theory also runs the risk of idealizing indigenous cultures, presenting them as perfect societies where women held significant power and lived without oppression. This idealization can obscure the realities and nuances of these societies, including internal conflicts, variations in gender roles across different tribes and regions, and the impact of external pressures such as colonization. Acknowledging these complexities is crucial to understanding the true nature of gender dynamics in indigenous societies.

Indigenous Feminism

Indigenous feminism integrates gender equity with cultural and spiritual traditions, asserting that women's empowerment is vital for community health (Gearon, 2021). Modern Indigenous feminists advocate for restoring traditional roles disrupted by colonialism and patriarchal systems (Gearon, 2021). Examining matriarchal societies in indigenous cultures challenges the Eurocentric view of women as subordinate. Scholars like Kears (2006) show that gender dynamics in these societies were more equitable and fluid than previously acknowledged.

Indigenous feminism aimed to reclaim and celebrate these traditional roles, advocating for the autonomy, agency, and power of Indigenous women within their communities (Gearon, 2021). It operates as an intersectional framework, intertwining feminism with decolonization efforts, Indigenous sovereignty, and human rights for Indigenous women and their families. This perspective aims to acknowledge, identify, and discard imposed worldviews, particularly patriarchal systems that grant men power and privilege at the expense of women, as well as marginalizing gay, queer, and transgender individuals. Within Indigenous communities, patriarchy distorted and suppressed Indigenous teachings on gender and sexuality, undermining

their diversity and significance (Gearon, 2021). Indigenous feminism focuses on collaborative empowerment, respecting the inherent worth of all community members.

The Challenges Within Indigenous Feminism

Indigenous feminism faces the challenge of avoiding the imposition of Western feminist ideals onto indigenous cultures, which often prioritize communal and relational values over individualism and gender equality. It's crucial to develop feminist frameworks that respect indigenous worldviews and cultural contexts. Additionally, Indigenous feminism must recognize the diverse identities and experiences among Indigenous women, considering intersecting forms of oppression based on race, class, sexuality, disability, and other factors, to address their needs.

Integrating Matriarchal Theory and Indigenous Feminism

Both matriarchal theory and Indigenous feminism offer valuable perspectives on the role of women within indigenous societies. While matriarchal theory highlights the historical agency and empowerment of women, Indigenous feminism provides a critical framework for challenging patriarchal systems and advancing the rights of Indigenous women. By engaging in dialogue and collaboration between these perspectives, we can address limitations, avoid reinforcing gender binaries, and honor traditional roles while embracing gender diversity. This inclusive approach promotes a fairer understanding of gender roles that recognizes the contributions of all community members, regardless of gender.

Respecting the cultural contexts of indigenous communities is crucial when applying feminist theories. This means valuing indigenous knowledge systems, traditions, and ways of life while working to dismantle oppressive structures. By grounding feminist efforts in the cultural realities of Indigenous peoples, we can ensure that these movements are transformative and supportive of indigenous sovereignty and self-determination. It is important to acknowledge the

insights of matriarchal theory and Indigenous feminism while addressing their limitations and avoiding the reinforcement of gender binaries or imposition of Western ideals. Through dialogue, respect for cultural contexts, and inclusive frameworks, we can leverage the strengths of both perspectives to advance the rights and well-being of all members of Indigenous communities.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology for this study employed a comprehensive and immersive approach to explore the roles of women and the dynamics of matriarchal traditions within Northern Thai societies, focusing on the Karen, Lahu, Lawa, and Lua ethnic groups, as well as the Tai Yuan, also called now *Khon Muang*.

The primary data collection was conducted through extensive field visits, participant observations, and community immersions in local villages of the Karen, Lahu, Lawa, Lua, and Tai Yuan people. The main researcher spent considerable time within these communities, engaging in direct observations to capture everyday practices, social interactions, and cultural rituals. This hands-on approach allowed researchers to observe daily life, participate in cultural events, and witness decision-making processes.

Participant observation was a key part of the methodology, allowing the researchers to immerse themselves in the daily life of the communities. By joining cultural events, religious ceremonies, and daily activities, the researcher experienced firsthand of social and cultural dynamics. Informal conversations with community members, including elders and women of different ages further enriched the understanding of local perspectives and historical roles of women.

The study used an integrated approach, combining fieldwork with extensive literature review and archival research. This involved reviewing scholarly articles, books, and historical records to provide a comprehensive understanding of Lanna traditions and matriarchal practices in Northern Thailand. By triangulating data from multiple sources, the research aimed to capture the dynamics of matriarchy, culture, and religious expressions within these communities. This dual approach ensured that the findings were grounded in both contemporary observations and historical contexts.

The data analysis involved thematic coding and narrative analysis. Thematic coding was used to identify recurring patterns and themes related to women's roles, matriarchal traditions, and cultural practices. Narrative analysis helped in understanding the stories and experiences shared by community members, providing a deeper insight into the cultural significance and personal meanings of these roles and traditions.

This methodological approach offers valuable contributions to the fields of gender studies, cultural anthropology, and regional analysis by focusing on the lived experiences and cultural contexts of women in Northern Thai societies. The comprehensive methodology ensures that the research findings are rooted in the cultural realities of the Karen, Lahu, Lawa, and Lua communities, providing a holistic perspective on the roles and contributions of women in Northern Thai society.

FINDINGS

Through an exploration of perceptions surrounding the role of women in family and community structures, the contribution of women in Northern Thai society, and the intricate line of matriarchy with cultural and religious frameworks, significant insights have been gathered.

These findings shed light on the dynamic relationship between gender dynamics, cultural norms, and societal structures in the context of Northern Thai communities. A deeper understanding emerges of the roles and influences of women within their respective societies.

Perceptions of the Role of Women in Family and Community Structures

Perceptions of the role of women in family and community structures in Northern Thailand reveal a unique societal framework where women are revered as central figures. Various aspects of daily life shaped these perceptions, including (a) women being perceived as heroes of the family, (b) women's roles in agriculture and trade, (c) and their spiritual significance as priestesses and healers. In contrast to other regions of Thailand, the Northern Thai communities emphasize the heroic and indispensable contributions of women, highlighting a cultural landscape where maternal strength and leadership are dominant.

A - Women as Heroes in the Family.

Perceptions within Northern Thai families and communal structures shape the experiences of women, with a notable absence of the father figure in family narratives. When individuals are asked to identify the most significant person in their family, they cite their mother, highlighting the essential role of women. Locals portrayed mothers as heroes, with narratives seldom mentioning fathers in this context.

In our informal conversations over the past few years with individuals in northern Thailand, a recurring theme has emerged: mothers are often highlighted as the most significant family members, sometimes alongside grandmothers or aunts who run businesses. Fathers, however, are seldom mentioned and are often portrayed as absent or disengaged from family affairs. This contrast underscores a cultural framework where mothers are central to family

stability and community cohesion, acting as primary caregivers, financial supporters, and moral guides, thereby emphasizing their indispensability within the family unit.

The importance of grandmothers and aunts who run businesses indicates a societal structure where women hold significant economic power, reinforcing their status as family heroes. This economic leadership challenges traditional gender roles and provides empowering role models for young women. The negative portrayal of men can perpetuate stereotypes that discourage male engagement in family life. These cultural narratives shape children's expectations and behaviors, with girls emulating their mothers' strength and boys lacking positive male role models. Promoting balanced representations of both parents could foster a more supportive family environment.

B - Women's role in agriculture and trade.

The significance of mothers and women in the Lanna region becomes evident during the harvest period. The entire family participates in this vital activity, but women assume more than a labor position. Women in Lanna society are involved in agricultural processes, from planting to harvesting, and their efforts are pivotal for the community's survival. According to research conducted by Disch in 2012, harvesting is linked with female fertility rituals. Their involvement in agriculture is not practical but also holds cultural and spiritual significance. Fertility rituals tied to harvesting reflect a deep-seated respect for women's contributions to agriculture, symbolizing their vital role in nurturing life and sustaining the community (Disch, 2012).

These fertility rituals celebrate women's crucial role in ensuring the community's well-being and continuity, emphasizing their importance beyond mere labor. Furthermore, women often engage in trade, both within and beyond their communities. They play key roles in local markets, selling produce and handmade goods, and contributing to the economic stability of their

families and communities. This involvement in trade provides women with a degree of economic independence and influence, further highlighting their integral role in society.

C - Women as “priestesses of nature”, mediums and healers.

Despite Buddhism's male-dominated spiritual power, women retain significant roles as nature priestesses, esteemed as mediums and healers with superior prophetic abilities. They are revered for healing ailments, predicting the future, and ensuring good harvests, making them indispensable to the community's spiritual and practical welfare. Most fortune-tellers are women, believed to provide more accurate predictions than men.

As researchers, we witnessed a healing ceremony in Lamphun City held in a public square dedicated to Queen Jamadewi. A woman with apparent healing abilities, channeling ancient spirits, assisted many individuals seeking aid. This public event featured traditional women's dances and offerings made to Queen Jamathewi's statue, exemplifying the enduring influence of women in spiritual practices beyond Buddhism.

Contributions of Women in Northern Thai Society

Women have contributed to the socio-cultural and religious framework of Northern Thai society through their roles and historical importance. Their contributions are cited as follows: (a) the autonomy of the local economy, business, and trade, (b) the influential roles of the queens, their exemptional leadership, and their military prowess, (c) women's contribution in the 20th century Lanna in the field of arts and crafts.

A - Autonomy of local economy, business, and trade.

Women have played a crucial role in Northern Thai society, contributing to the local economy, business, and trade. They have achieved economic autonomy through their

involvement in agriculture, crafts, and retail. Dominating commerce and owning the majority of small businesses, women are key players in local markets, street vending, and small-scale manufacturing. Their management of these enterprises secures economic independence and contributes to the community's economic stability and growth. Despite men holding political power, women have maintained control over local economic activities, highlighting their essential role in community prosperity (Tantiwiranond & Pandey, 1987).

Historically, women have been significant figures in business, even during periods of economic transition. In the 16th century, European and Chinese traders were surprised to find themselves negotiating with women in Thailand (Disch, 2012). This tradition continues, with women holding 40% of top executive positions in Thailand as of 2012, a rate second globally (Disch, 2012). Matrilineal inheritance and matrilocal residence patterns in many Northern Thai communities empower women by granting them control over land and resources, supporting their economic activities and community involvement (Disch, 2012).

B - Influential role of the queens – their exceptional leadership & military prowess.

Historical figures like Queen Jamadewi and Queen Chamari exemplify the influential roles women have played in shaping Northern Thailand's history and religious landscape. Queen Jamadewi, the first sovereign of Hariphunchai, promoted Buddhism and defended her region's independence, challenging traditional gender roles. Her leadership and military prowess were instrumental in establishing and consolidating power in her kingdom (Disch, 2012).

Queen Chamari is another significant figure, known for leading her people to safety and founding the Kingdom of Li, a land characterized by arts and religious prosperity.¹ She prioritized

¹ The main researcher visited and photographed the 91 images in this temple, thus the main reference for this section are the images found in the temple and the narrative text engraved in each of the images.

amicable relations and commercial ties, fostering a peaceful and thriving community. Her decision not to marry and her focus on leadership exemplify feminist ideals (Disch, 2012).

The legend of Queen Malika² (region of Fang, north of Chiang Mai province), further exemplifies the empowerment of women in Northern Thai society. Queen Malika, known for her martial arts mastery, symbolizes independence and strength. Ruling over the Kingdom of Mae Ai, she commanded an army of female warriors and is still venerated today, with annual ceremonies commemorating her contributions (Sarataru, 2017).

In the realm of politics, women played significant roles during periods of turmoil and rebellion. Queens such as Phra Nang Chiraprapa and Wisutthithewi were called upon to ascend the throne in times of crisis, showcasing their ability to provide stability and leadership during challenging times (Wyatt & Wichienkeo, 1998). Their ascension to power was not a mere filling of a vacancy but a strategic choice to leverage their unique leadership qualities during critical periods. These queens demonstrated exceptional political judgment and successfully found peaceful resolutions to direct military attacks through a visionary approach. Their reigns challenged traditional patriarchal norms and highlighted the importance of female leadership in governance and cultural influence.

The role of "Phu Yai Baan," or village elder, further highlights women's influence in Northern Thai society. Often elected for their deep knowledge of the community, women Phu Yai Baan oversee local administration and conflict resolution, maintaining social cohesion and community well-being (Panitchaphan, 2005). Elected for four-year terms by the villagers to oversee local administration, the Phu Yai Baan's duties include decision-making, conflict

² Source: interpretive Panel of national Park in Fang. Blog: <http://chamadewi.blogspot.com/2017/07/blog-post.html>

resolution, and representing the village to authorities, ensuring social cohesion and community well-being. Women are often considered better choices for community leadership, according to Panitchaphan (2005), due to the matrilineal societal foundation of Northern Thailand, women, in general, do not move around much, allowing them to know their community and their own history very well.

C - Women in the 20th Century Lanna in the Fields of Arts and Crafts.

In contemporary times, figures like Dara Rasami, daughter of the final monarch of Chiang Mai, have left a lasting legacy. Married to King Rama V of Siam, Dara Rasami dedicated herself to preserving Lanna's traditions. She supported artisans, dancers, and monasteries, ensuring the continuation of cultural heritage (Castro -Woodhouse, 2021). Her influence is still evident in Lanna culture, with her efforts celebrated at the Daraphirom Palace Museum in Chiang Mai.

She provided support to artisans and tailors to uphold ancient weaving techniques, sponsored dancers to safeguard intangible heritage, and patronized monasteries to maintain Lanna architecture amid the spread of central Thai styles (Castro- Woodhouse, 2021). Her story is known in today's society in northern Thailand. The house where she lived in northern Chiang Mai during the latter part of her life has been transformed into a museum, the Daraphirom Palace Museum (Mae Rim), where visitors can learn about her life surrounded by her personal belongings. The influence of Dara Rasami is woven into Lanna culture. You cannot witness a Lanna dance or observe the complex patterns of a "sarong" without recalling her contributions. Her legacy ensures that these cultural treasures remain vibrant and cherished. At the opening ceremony of the Annual International Conference on Religion, Culture, and Peace Education at Payap University, Chiang Mai, Thailand, we were privileged to witness two dancers whose

performance was not merely artistic but also carried profound symbolic significance. Without the efforts of Dara Rasami, these dances risked fading into obscurity in today's cultural landscape.

The Three Kings statue in Chiang Mai, commemorating the historic alliance between King Mengrai and his allies, located in the city's central square, is a monument of great symbolic importance. It is the work of Khun Kaimook Chuto, the first Thai female sculptor. Appointed as a royal sculptor by Queen Sirikit, her work broke traditional gender barriers in a field typically dominated by men. Her contributions to Thai sculpture are significant, and her legacy is celebrated, including recognition by Google in 2017 (Unsup, 2004).

Today, these women are revered for their courage, embodying ancient cultural values and offering spiritual guidance and assistance in various aspects of daily life. Temples, shrines, statues, and annual festivals commemorate their contributions, keeping their legacies alive in the collective memory of Northern Thai society. Their stories are integral to the culture and spirituality, providing role models for contemporary women and reinforcing the cultural belief in the potential and capability of female leaders.

The Impact of Matriarchy on the Cultural and Religious Landscape of Northern Thailand

The matriarchal traditions of Northern Thailand, showed through matrilineal power structures, spiritual practices, and the valorization of the female authority, have influenced the region's cultural and religious landscape. This imprint manifests through: (a) legacy of ancient legends, (b) influence on Lanna communities, (c) structuring role within ethnic groups, (d) permeation of local spirituality, (e) repercussions on masculine identities, (f) interactions with Buddhism.

A - Matriarchal legends and folklore about nature and spirits.

Northern Thais revere female nature spirits, such as Doi Nang-Non, Mae Nangkeo, and Bua Tong, as guardians of the environment and fertility. These legends highlight powerful female figures, symbolizing resilience, sacrifice, and leadership in the region's folklore. Princesses in ancient legends play central roles, discovering water sources in caves or shaping mountain ranges, leaving enduring marks on narratives.

The 2018 incident of the trapped footballers in Chiang Rai cave sparked speculation about the presence of the mythical princess, Jao Mae Nang Non, haunting the cave. Some believed she was involved in the boys' disappearance. Villagers invoked her spirit during rescue efforts, reflecting the lasting impact of matriarchal legends on Northern Thai society, influencing cultural practices, and elevating the status of women.

Today, these women are revered for their strength, courage, and embodiment of ancient cultural values. Their worship reflects regional patriotism, with some considering it fashionable to appreciate Lanna's specificities. Additionally, as many of these female spirits are associated with love stories, young couples often make offerings to them in caves, seeking luck in their relationships.

B - Matrilineal transmission of power and property in the Lanna communities.

Matriarchy influences Northern Thailand's culture and religion, contrasting with patriarchal norms in Buddhism. In the group now identify as “Khon Muang”, the mother symbolizes female power, with women dominating the household domain. Men join their wives' families through marriage. Matrilineal systems prevail, shaping social organization and inheritance. Women hold central roles in decision-making, property ownership, and clan leadership, respected for their skills and leadership qualities. Matrilineal transmission of power and property highlights the elevated status of women, who are respected for their skills and

qualities as inventors, leaders, and decision-makers. Grandmothers and elder women are revered as matriarchs, preserving family culture and knowledge. Their authority extends to crucial rituals like marriage and inheritance (Satyawadhna, 1991; Forbes & Henley, 1997).

In northern Thai households, decisions are made near the loom, a symbol of women's authority (Panitchaphan, 2005). Traditional marriage among the Lanna people is not a complicated ceremony. The groom bows his head at the altar of the bride's female ancestors with offerings, then he can move into his wife's family home. The bride's parents tie bracelets of good fortune on the bride and groom, and the ceremony is complete. The young couple enjoys the privilege of the first room until they establish descendants for the clan. Afterward, the man's presence becomes optional, and he may construct a bamboo shelter in the garden (Panitchaphan, 2005).

The Matriarchal and Matrilineal Traditions in Ethnic Villages

North of Thailand, on the margins of lowland peoples such as the Tai, Lawa, and Lua, live the hill peoples or "hill tribes" - the Karens, Hmongs, Lahus, Lisus, Akhas, and Yaos. These six minority ethnic groups are distinguished by their ways of life, traditional costumes, languages, and rich unique histories. Although sharing some similarities, each of these mountain peoples has its own customs and age-old traditions (Lewis & Lewis, 1984).

Among them, the Karens and Lahus are recognized for their matriarchal societal structure, where women play a predominant role in family and community. These mountain ethnic groups in northern Thailand are known as "transnational communities" due to their presence spanning regions from Myanmar to Laos. Their history is marked by forced displacements, and many still lead semi-nomadic lifestyles, moving between countries to practice traditional agriculture. This

perpetual mobility reflects their deep connection to nature and seasonal cycles. (Lewis & Lewis, 1984)

The Karen Tribe

The Karen society, residing in provinces like Chiang Mai, Mae Hong Son, and Tak, Thailand as well as across the border in Myanmar's Karen State, identifies itself as matriarchal and matrilineal. In this social structure, women hold the position of spiritual clan leaders within the family. Upon marriage, husbands join their wives' families, integrating into their wives' clans. This multi-generational family setup often sees daughters and their husbands residing with the wife's parents to provide care. In cases of divorce, the children remain with the mother, reflecting the matrilineal emphasis of Karen society (Karen Organization of Minnesota, 2017).

In traditional Karen societies, some marriages are arranged by families. If a young Karen man is interested in a girl, he expresses his intentions through a letter. The entire village often weighs in on the suitability of a marriage, considering it unwise to upset the spirits. Thus, while the opinion of the young girl is considered, the community's perspective usually holds precedence (Karen Organization of Minnesota, 2017). Within Karen households, women hold significant authority, overseeing domestic tasks and agricultural work. Men primarily engage in fieldwork. Women serve as heads of the spiritual clan and the main lineage, playing a central role in organizing the household (EthnoMed, 2008).

Abigaël Pesses' thesis (2004) investigates into the socio-cultural and ecological aspects of the Karen ethnic group in Thailand. Through fieldwork in a Karen village in Chiang Mai province, she gathered crucial data on their contemporary lifestyle. Pesses (2004) emphasizes the matriarchal nature of Karen society, where women play a central role in managing the family and domestic affairs, despite appearing reserved to outsiders. While men hold formal positions,

decisions often originate from consultations led by women within households. A notable example is the selection of a Village Chief, where men's discussions reflect prior consultations conducted by their wives. This highlights the significant decision-making power held by Karen women, who prioritize the well-being of the family and community.

The Lahu Tribe

The Lahu People did not arrive in northern Thailand until the 19th century. The Lahu originate from southwestern China. The Lahu are matrilineal but claim to be egalitarian in decision-making. (Lewis & Lewis, 1984). Du Shanshan's book (2002) "Chopsticks Only Work in Pairs: Gender Unity and Gender Equality Among the Lahu of Southwestern China," underscores the ingrained principles of gender unity and equality within Lahu culture in China. This concept of equality and mutual support between men and women appears to be embraced by the Lahu community residing in Thailand (Lahu individual, personal communication, May 31, 2024).

In Thai Lahu villages, responsibilities are equitably distributed between genders. Women manage domestic and agricultural tasks, while men engage in fieldwork. However, this division of labor does not suggest a hierarchical structure or the dominance of one gender over the other (Facts and Details, 2022). Important decisions within the household are made jointly by the spouses. The Lahu family structure is based on an egalitarian system where decision-making power is shared between men and women. This equality is also reflected in Lahu marriage traditions. Unlike many patriarchal societies, young Lahu have great freedom of choice in choosing their partner. Arranged marriages are rare, thus reinforcing women's autonomy. (Facts and Details, 2022)

The Lua Tribe

In the remote valleys of Nan Province, Thailand, some villages maintain the ancient Lua traditions despite integration into the Khon Muang or Lanna group. Anthropologist Dr. Cholthira Satyawadhna's study of a remote Lua community in Nan Province reveals the significant role of women. Women wield authority in household and decision-making matters, with husbands consulting them on all major expenditures, reflecting economic power in female hands (Satyawadhna, 1991). During a post-conflict period in a mountainous region, Satyawadhna researched a Lua village's traditional lifestyle. Emerging from a period of Communist insurgency (1967-1982), she observed matriarchal leaders determining rice allocation for rebel troops and deciding on children joining guerrilla forces (Satyawadhna, 1991).

The Lua uphold ancestral matriarchal traditions where women lead the clan (cao kok) beyond the family unit. In their society, descent, property, and privileges pass exclusively through the maternal line. Matrilineal principles govern everything from rituals to power succession to marriages. Before marriage, the groom must perform the "tat phii" ritual, seeking approval from his and the bride's matrilineal spirits. Leadership within Lua clans, inherited by the eldest female descendant, underscores the matrilineal lineage's importance. The "matrilineal liquor pot" symbolizes this lineage's continuity, embodying the authority of each new chief. Even if a male chief marries another clan's cao kok, his wife assumes authority, reflecting the preeminence of female lineage in Lua society (Satyawadhna, 1991).

Since this study dates back to 1991, the matrilineal lifestyle and social organization of Lua may have evolved due to factors like education, rural exodus, and changing mindsets. An updated field study is needed to assess the persistence or erosion of these traditions over the past 30 years.

Women perform trance dances, feminine energy, and ancestral spirits.

Spiritual practices, such as trance dances serve as a means of communicating with the spirits. Traditional trance dance in the northern Thai population has long been an important activity as a gesture of homage and respect to the spirits of their ancestral roots. This form of animist practice appears to originate from pre-Buddhist culture, as suggested by the costumes, musical melodies, types of drums used, and musical instruments (Panitchaphan, 2005). These ceremonial trance dances, organized annually or based on financial circumstances, are led by the matriarch of each clan. They may also be held after illnesses or as a thanksgiving for good fortune. Mainly maternal kin participate, while paternal kin rarely do. The dances occur at the house of the oldest woman, "Gao Pi," who invites the ancestral spirits and enters the trance first, accompanied by ancient music. Men can observe from a distance but are instructed not to approach the ritual space instruments (Panitchaphan, 2005). During the clan's trance dances, members gradually enter trance, shaking, jerking, and shouting. Spirit-possessed women inquire about the younger generation's well-being, offer healing, give advice, predict futures, and address inappropriate behavior. They also reinforce taboos and traditions to ensure the clan's continuity. Accompanied by alcohol consumption, these dances are a unique way of communicating with spirits. Unlike the patriarchal traditions of China and India, these Lanna dances emphasize reverence for feminine energies (Panitchaphan, 2005).

Societal ideals of strength and power are more associated with femininity than masculinity.

The region's positive portrayal of women is reflected in the acceptance of transgender individuals, or "katoeys." These individuals are seen as resilient and assertive, indicating that strength and authority are linked with femininity rather than masculinity. This favorable view likely influences

many boys to transition. "Katoeys" embody determination and empowerment, highlighting society's perception that strength and authority are more associated with femininity (Panitchaphan, 2005).

Panitchaphan (2005) notes that over the past 40 years, more and more men, gay boys, and many transvestites have been involved in trance dance activities. These transgender individuals are increasingly taking the place of women in this ritual activity. Although the event itself takes place in traditional local communities, transgenders are widely accepted in this traditional role.

Women in Buddhism: Transformation and Symbolism in Lanna Culture.

Buddhism, predominantly led by male clergy, historically views women as impure and restricts their entry into certain temple areas. Women are not to touch monks, as outlined in the Vinaya, the monastic discipline code (Sirisai et al., 2017). Despite this, women play crucial roles in supporting monks, cooking meals, and maintaining temple cleanliness, often dedicating more time to these tasks than men.

The Mae Chi, an equivalent of a nun, represents an ambivalent position between the ascetic and secular worlds. They observe the Eight Precepts and renounce worldly pleasures by shaving their hair, wearing white robes, and taking vows of abstinence. However, they are not considered part of the "merit field" like monks, who follow 227 monastic rules. Their white robe symbolizes their lower status. This role did not exist in Buddhism's original four orders (Tantiwiranond & Pandey, 1987). The arrival of Buddhism shifted Lanna culture, emphasizing men, leaders, lords, and monks. Men now play a larger role in beliefs and rituals, while women's roles in spirit worship persist. Monks seek to diminish spirit worship, deeming it superstitious (Panitchaphan 2005).

The ancient view of women as nature goddesses was integrated into Lanna Buddhism. Wright (1990) states Buddhism preserved pre-Buddhist terrestrial religion in art, architecture, ritual, and history. When Buddha meditated under the Bodhi tree, he invoked Earth as a witness, and Phra Mae Thorani, the goddess of nature, helped him by washing away demons. This event is depicted in many Thai Buddhist temples, with statues of Phra Mae Thorani symbolizing Mother Nature present in most temples.

The creation myths of Northern Thais highlight the ancient importance of women as the first creators of life and spirit, as shown in the Lanna tradition's *Pathamamulamuli*. This myth describes a "Grandmother" who created the first humans and assigned them three genders: male, female, and transgender (Anatole-Roger Peltier, cited in Hongsuwan, 2024). This founding myth emphasizes a goddess woman as humanity's creator. Every human is believed to be born of this creator grandmother, reflecting the feminine image in body and spirit. Respecting women has ancient roots, linking women to divinity and fertility due to their ability to give birth and nurture children (Hongsuwan, 2024).

In the households of northern Thailand, decisions are made near the loom. When Panitchaphan wrote this, it means that working at the loom is as important as working in the fields or any other task. The loom is not a subordinate task, but rather the work of women who hold power. This implies that in the matriarchal societies of Northern Thailand, women do not abandon "women's work" to focus only on power. Tasks are distributed among individuals, and matriarchy is not a reversal of power compared to the patriarchal system. Instead, it is a peaceful balance where everyone engages in tasks recognized as being of equal value.

DISCUSSION

Exploring Women's Influence in Peacebuilding in Northern Thai Society

The exploration of women's roles in peacebuilding within Northern Thai society reveals the significant impact of women in family, community, and broader societal structures. Societal norms in this region celebrate women's strength and resilience, portraying them as the heroes who sustain family cohesion and welfare. Legendary accounts of queens who ruled during times of turmoil and chaos – when no qualified men could lead highlight their abilities to defend territories and promote cultural and religious advancements. Their legacies challenge traditional gender roles, showcasing women's capabilities in governance and military strategy.

The cultural and social dynamics of Northern Thai society, rooted in the reverence for women as life-givers and nurturers, translate into a social structure where women were central figures in maintaining community welfare. This reverence extends beyond biological roles to encompass broader community responsibilities, including agricultural management, conflict resolution, and education of the young. The respect for women's wisdom and experience, particularly that of elderly women, ensured that their voices are central to governance and social cohesion. Elderly women, often seen as repositories of cultural knowledge and experience, play crucial roles in mediating conflicts and guiding community decisions, reinforcing the importance of inclusive and participatory governance structures.

Women's influence in peacebuilding within Northern Thai society involves a complex interplay of gender dynamics, cultural norms, and societal structures. Women are celebrated as central figures in family and community life, vital contributors to the local economy, and influential spiritual leaders. The matriarchal elements within Northern Thai culture further elevate women's status, highlighting their integral role in maintaining social and cultural cohesion. These

insights emphasize the profound impact women have on the socio-cultural and religious life of Northern Thai communities, challenging traditional patriarchal norms and emphasizing their essential contributions to societal well-being.

The concept of gender balance and peace in matriarchal societies is intertwined with the principles of shared responsibilities and maternal values. These societies emphasize an ethic of balance and harmony, contrasting with patriarchal structures that often prioritize hierarchical dominance and competition. In matriarchal societies, men and women share responsibilities. This fair distribution and mutual respect in performing social, economic, and political roles differ from having distinct roles for both genders. For instance, while men may take on certain public leadership roles, women often manage community resources and maintain social networks that are crucial for conflict resolution and community resilience.

We argue that societies with maternal values foster an ethic of gender balance and peace. These values focus on cooperation, partnership, and nurturing, which contrast with the competitive and often violent ethos seen in patriarchal systems. We emphasize that matriarchy is not about female dominance but about foundational maternal values that promote balance and peace. In the face of modern challenges such as environmental degradation, the principles of matriarchal societies offer a blueprint for a more harmonious and sustainable world. These principles include peace, partnership, balance, and respect for differences. Integrating these values into global culture can help address the crises facing humanity today. For example, environmental stewardship often aligns with maternal values of nurturing and sustaining life, suggesting that matriarchal principles could guide more effective and compassionate environmental policies.

Matriarchal societies, by fostering an ethic of balance and peace through shared responsibilities and maternal principles, present a compelling alternative to patriarchal systems. They emphasize the importance of nurturing social ties, cooperative leadership, and sustaining harmonious relationships. In a world facing significant social and environmental challenges, the values of matriarchy offer a path toward a more balanced and peaceful global culture. Embracing these values could lead to a society where cooperation and mutual respect are paramount, and where the well-being of the community is prioritized over individual competition and dominance. By looking to the matriarchal traditions of Northern Thai society, we can learn valuable lessons about creating more inclusive, resilient, and peaceful communities worldwide.

SUMMARY

This study investigates the interplay of patriarchy and matriarchy in Northern Thai society, particularly within Lanna traditions. Women's pivotal roles in decision-making, property ownership, and spiritual practices showcase their agency and influence in familial and communal contexts. They often manage household finances and inherit land, ensuring their centrality in economic and social spheres.

Women's autonomy is vital in Northern Thai society, particularly in local economies. They play crucial roles in agriculture and trade, managing production, distribution, and market activities. They negotiate prices, run businesses, and demonstrate leadership and entrepreneurial skills in various economic endeavors, from small-scale trading to large market operations. Additionally, women lead in community affairs, resolving conflicts and guiding communal decisions, further solidifying their influential role in Northern Thai society.

Northern Thai spirituality intertwines patriarchal Buddhism with reverence for female deities and animist traditions, creating a unique spiritual landscape. Female spiritual leaders, like priestesses and mediums, play essential roles, in connecting women with the spiritual realm. Matrifocal orientation is evident in the veneration of female spirits and the celebration of women in legends and folklore

Women's influence in preserving cultural heritage is evident through oral traditions, storytelling, and participation in festivals. Among ethnic groups like the Karen and Lahu, matrilineal inheritance practices reinforce women's roles as decision-makers and cultural custodians. Property and wealth passing through the female line empower women and ensure cultural continuity and social stability.

In Northern Thailand, a balanced approach to power-sharing between men and women fosters communal leadership and decision-making. Women's crucial roles in household and local economy management, alongside men, ensure diverse perspectives in decision-making. This inclusive model challenges patriarchal norms, offering a balance framework for governance and community organization, and advocating for egalitarian social structures.

CONCLUSION

By appreciating the diverse contributions of women, we gain a deeper understanding of the complex societal frameworks that shape Northern Thai culture. Despite the coexistence of patriarchal norms, matriarchal traditions persist, offering alternative perspectives on leadership, spirituality, and community dynamics. These insights challenge conventional narratives of male dominance and highlight the potential for more egalitarian social structures. The recognition of women's pivotal roles in economic, cultural, and spiritual domains emphasizes their indispensable

contribution to the region's identity and development. These traditions provide a model of gender balance and respect that stands in contrast to more rigid patriarchal systems. By appreciating the diverse contributions of women, we gain a deeper understanding of the complex societal frameworks that shape Northern Thai culture and the vital roles women play within it.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To advance women's empowerment in Northern Thailand, integrating research insights into education and community initiatives is crucial. Educators and leaders can create inclusive learning environments by incorporating diverse perspectives on gender roles and cultural traditions into the curriculum. This includes revising textbooks to feature more female historical figures and leaders from Northern Thailand. Cultural events and workshops celebrating matriarchal traditions can also promote gender equity. Encouraging student-led projects and discussions on gender roles and cultural heritage further empowers young women to embrace their heritage and potential.

Policymakers and stakeholders should prioritize initiatives supporting the preservation and celebration of matriarchal traditions in Northern Thailand. This includes funding cultural preservation projects and creating spaces for women to share their stories. Policymakers should also implement policies promoting gender equity in education, employment, and healthcare. This could involve providing scholarships and mentorship programs for young women and implementing gender-sensitive workplace policies.

Community initiatives should empower women at the grassroots level by supporting women's groups and cooperatives engaged in economic activities. Providing resources and

training enhances women's economic independence and leadership roles. Promoting women's participation in local governance ensures their voices are heard and contributions recognized.

Embracing gender dynamics and cultural heritage allows Northern Thailand to evolve as an inclusive society valuing all members' contributions. This involves acknowledging women's historical and cultural significance and creating environments for them to thrive and contribute. These efforts can make Northern Thailand a model for other regions, showcasing the benefits of inclusivity and equity.

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